

2025

Warner Valley

MEADOW AND RIVERSCAPE CONDITION ASSESSMENT

Prepared by Trout Unlimited in partnership with the Friends of Warner Valley
and the Sierra Institute for Community and Environment

Summary

This comprehensive assessment integrates an analysis of historical conditions, including land-use patterns, disturbances, and long-term vegetative trends, with a contemporary evaluation of riverscape health, hydrogeomorphology, and landcover mapping. The assessment revealed that the meadow and riverscape are in a favorable ecological state and exhibit high functionality, despite the adverse effects of the 2021 Dixie Fire and historical land-use practices. The primary threat to the valley’s valuable rare fen and wet meadow habitats lies in a long-term trend of diminishing perennial herbaceous cover and concurrent conifer encroachment, which is indicative of a declining water table due to spring-fed channels becoming structurally starved, incised, and disconnected from adjacent surfaces. Conversely, the main Warner Creek channel demonstrates a relatively high degree of instream habitat complexity and follows a trend of increased riparian vegetation density. To mitigate the drying trend and preserve fragile meadow habitat, the report recommends low-impact, process-based restoration strategies, specifically manual conifer reduction and the installation of Beaver Dam Analogues (BDAs) in spring channels. These measures aim to restore water table elevation, enhance floodplain connectivity, and facilitate the expansion of wet-meadow habitat.

Figure 1. A panoramic view of an expansive fen situated within the Warner Valley Wildlife Management Area. The photograph was captured during an assessment scoping visit in mid-June 2025.

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1. Assessment Introduction and Approach

The Warner Valley meadow area is an ecologically significant high-elevation mountain valley situated near the southern edge of the Cascade Mountain Range. Primarily within Plumas County, California, its watershed originates on the southern slope of Mt. Lassen. The region's geography is defined by a landscape shaped by recent volcanic activity and glacial processes. The local climate is typical of the Northern California mountains, characterized by cold, snowy winters and dry, mild summers. Geologically, the area is situated on volcanic bedrock, which heavily influences its hydrology. This results in the presence of numerous thermal features and a unique hydrological regime that sustains the valley's primary ecological feature: a complex network of rare fen and meadow habitats. The valley's extensive fens and peat-accumulating wetlands fed by mineral-rich groundwater support distinct and rare plant communities, and play a vital role in regional water resources and biodiversity.

Figure 2. In the Warner Valley meadow, a close-up photo captures a sundew (Drosera sp.), a carnivorous plant often referred to as a "flypaper plant." These plants thrive in the wet-meadow environments of Warner Valley meadow where they inhabit the peat-forming fens.

1.1. Historic Land Use and Natural Disturbance

The present-day structure of the Warner Valley meadow complex is a direct result of both historical human activity and natural disturbance regimes. Early Euro-American settlement in the surrounding area began in the mid-19th century, leading to intensive logging and ranching use. The valley's wet meadows were historically subjected to draining and ditching to maximize forage production, fundamentally altering the natural hydrology and potentially accelerating peat loss in the sensitive fen areas. Further significant impact came from commercial livestock grazing, which persisted across the landscape until the State of California authorized the purchase of the 689-acre Warner Valley Wildlife Area in 1987 and removed grazing entirely in 1991. The most recent and dramatic disturbance was the 2021 Dixie Fire, which heavily impacted the valley, burning through large tracts of forest and meadow habitat and initiating a new phase of ecological succession and land management challenges related to post-fire erosion and recovery.

Figure 3. A comprehensive chronological overview of significant anthropogenic and natural disturbances that have influenced meadow conditions within Warner Valley over the past century.

1.2. Assessment Objectives

The current assessment is driven by the intrinsic ecological value of Warner Valley and its susceptibility to disturbances such as the recent catastrophic fire event and potential impacts arising from climate change as well as a legacy of impacts of over a century and a half of post-European settlement activities and management. This assessment aims to synthesize available

natural historical and contemporary ecological observations to analyze the current state of the meadow system, evaluate the specific ecological consequences of past and recent disturbances, and provide a scientifically sound framework for future management activities. The objective is to ensure the conservation of the valley's unique hydrology and rare fen biodiversity. Specifically, the assessment is designed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Incorporate field observations with available geospatial datasets to evaluate the historic and current state of meadow and fluvial environments in Warner Valley.
2. Provide a baseline set of monitoring indicators and associated data sources that can be used to quantitatively track the future trajectory of meadow and fluvial habitat in response to changing climatic conditions or the effectiveness of restoration and management actions.
3. Propose restoration and management measures that could foster preservation and enhancement of aquatic and meadow habitat in Warner Valley.

The assessment is structured in accordance with an evaluation of long-term historical trends (2) as well as contemporary (3) riverscape and meadow composition and condition. The historic assessment primarily relies on remotely sensed time-series datasets that span almost 4 decades (e.g., Landsat datasets from 1986 to the present). Contemporary conditions are characterized through a comprehensive approach that integrates field observations with the analysis and interpretation of high-resolution orthoimagery and elevation datasets.

Figure 4. The general assessment spatial scope covers approximately 4.3 miles of Warner Valley, primarily consisting of state lands managed by the California Fish and Game Wildlife Area. Maps also show the approximate valley bottom of Warner Valley, which provided a general lateral extent for this assessment.

1.3. Assessment Scope

This assessment encompasses approximately 4.3 linear miles of Warner Valley at the southern border of Lassen National Park, from the junction of Hot Springs and Kings Creek to below the Chester Warner Valley Road bridge (Figure 4). The lateral extent of the assessment encompasses the approximate valley bottom area of Warner Valley, characterized by a width ranging between 0.2 and 0.5 miles between the valley hillslopes. This area of Warner Valley is believed to contain two distinct hydrologic process zones that operate independently. These zones include the meadow proper, which is primarily influenced by groundwater and spring channels, and the floodplain and active channel, which is influenced by fluvial processes associated with Warner Creek. Consequently, a preliminary step in this assessment involved the separation of the assessment extent into distinct hydrologic process zones. This process was informed by the evaluation of valley bottom topographic features as well as meadow and hydrogeomorphic indicators (Figure 5).

This initial classification of dominant process spaces within the project area will provide context for numerous analytical summaries presented in this assessment.

LiDAR Data and Process Zones
Warner Valley Meadow Assessment

0 1 2 mi

Figure 5. Valley cross-sections taken from LiDAR based relative elevation models and showing primary riverscape features and approximate transition between riverine influenced and wet meadow influenced zones. See above for approximate cross-section locations.

2. Long-Term Composition and Condition

The long-term composition and condition of Warner Valley were assessed employing two methodologies: 1) by utilizing remotely sensed datasets within contemporary geospatial analysis platforms to monitor alterations in vegetation composition and condition, and 2) by analyzing historical orthoimagery to discern readily observable modifications to the meadow or riverscape.

Figure 6. In late summer 2025, a north-facing view of the Warner Valley meadow reveals a mosaic of vegetation types across the valley floor. This mosaic encompasses riparian shrub species (mostly willow and alder), herbaceous meadow areas characterized by grasses, sedges, and hydric forbs, standing and downed pine trees burned in the 2021 fire, and dense stands of encroaching pines.

2.1. Historic Climate Trends

Historic large-scale trends in climate and vegetation composition and condition can now be readily analyzed using modern geospatial platforms like Climate Engine. These platforms leverage vast archives of satellite imagery, such as data from Landsat and MODIS, coupled with powerful cloud computing and analytical tools. This allows processing time-series data spanning decades, allowing researchers and land managers to rapidly detect and quantify changes, such as shifts in forest cover, rangeland health, or wildfire recovery.

Figure 7. Trends in precipitation (lower panel) and drought severity as indicated by SPEI (upper panel). The blue lines in both figures depicts the linear trend observed in the data. SPEI values approaching 2 indicate wet periods, while -2 indicates severe drought conditions. Note the overall downward trend in precipitation over the measured time span.

Climate was characterized by evaluating the NCLIM precipitation data, a gridded historical record of precipitation, and the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), a multi-scalar drought index that combines precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (PET). The SPEI is particularly relevant to climate change because it accounts for the effect of rising temperatures on water demand (via PET), which directly links to vegetation health by quantifying the overall water deficit or surplus experienced by ecosystems over various time scales. SPEI values are interpreted such that negative numbers correspond to drought conditions (water deficit), with increasingly negative values indicating greater severity, and positive numbers correspond to wet periods (water surplus).

2.1.1. Long-Term Climate Trend Interpretation

INCREASING DROUGHT SEVERITY – Long-term trends in SPEI suggest a trend towards increasing drought conditions since 1986 (Figure 7).

DECREASING PRECIPITATION – Annual total precipitation shows a decreasing trend.

SEVERE DROUGHT IN 2021 – Long-term trends are partly driven by severe drought of 2021 that corresponded with severe the Dixie fire.

2.2. Vegetative and Land-Cover Composition

Historic trends in vegetative cover composition for meadow areas of Warner Valley (Figure 5) were evaluated from within Climate Engine by leveraging land-cover datasets produced by the USDA’s Range Analysis Platform (RAP, Harrison 2025). These datasets combine 30 m Landsat data with field observations to produce annual estimates of vegetative ground cover composition (see Figure 8 for example of RAP datasets). The RAP datasets were used to identify trends in the vegetative cover of the meadow portions of Warner Valley (see Figure 5 above for approximate area of the analysis).

Figure 8. Visualization of the RAP (Range Analysis Platform) datasets for Warner Valley. The raster datasets depict the annual estimate of % tree cover (inclusive of conifers and deciduous shrubs and trees) for 1986, 2005, and 2024.

Table 1. Range Analysis Platform landcover classification descriptions and interpretation.

RAP Landcover Class	Description	Interpretation
<i>Tree</i>	Inclusive of conifers and deciduous trees and shrubs including riparian shrubs (e.g., alder, willow).	Woody encroachment or forest cover. A high or increasing trend suggests rangeland conversion to forest or shrubland dominance and generally reducing herbaceous cover. This includes riparian hardwoods such as willow and alder that grow along stream channels and the river bottom.
<i>Perennial Forb & Grass</i>	Native/desirable perennial grasses and forbs (including sedges, rushes, and flowering plants)	Meadow/rangeland health. High cover suggests a healthy, resilient, and productive herbaceous understory (i.e., Herbaceous Meadow/Fen areas).
<i>Annual Forb & Grass</i>	Non-native annual grasses and forbs (e.g., Cheatgrass, Red Brome, annual weeds)	Invasive annual cover / fire risk. High cover often indicates degraded range condition and is highly correlated with increased wildfire frequency and intensity.
<i>Shrub</i>	Small woody shrubs such as sagebrush and greasewood.	Shrub cover that is typical of shrub-steppe but can also indicate succession toward shrub dominance or poor fire return intervals in other areas.
<i>Bare Ground</i>	Exposed mineral soil and rocks	Erosion risk. High cover suggests poor soil stability, severe drought, or excessive disturbance (e.g., heavy grazing).

Figure 9. Vegetation cover composition from the Range Analysis Platform classification of Landsat imagery from 1986 – present.

2.2.1. Long-Term Vegetation and Cover Trend and Interpretation

BARE GROUND AND INVASIVES NEGLIGIBLE - The presence of bare ground and annuals, which serve as a close indicator of invasive grasses, has remained low and static within meadow areas.

STABLE SHRUB COVER - Average shrub cover in general has remained relatively constant through the period of recover at between 10% and 20%.

INCREASED CONIFER AND RIPARIAN HARDWOOD COVER – There is an overall discernible trend of diminishing perennial herbaceous vegetation cover and increasing tree cover, though a major dip in tree cover corresponds with the intensive 4-year drought period from 2012 to 2015 that may have resulted in mortality due to bark beetles and drought stress. This shift corresponds with the decline of herbaceous meadow and potentially peat-forming fen habitats, with a concurrent increase in both conifer and riparian hardwood cover. The increase in conifer encroachment is a symptom of decreased water table elevation and soil saturation in the wet meadow/fen habitats. The increase in riparian hardwood cover likely corresponds to the change in grazing management

and removal of livestock grazing from the CDFW property that has allowed alder and willow galleries to grow along stream channels.

EVIDENCE OF BEETLE KILL IN 2011 – 2016 – The significant reduction in tree cover is likely a direct consequence of beetle-infested conifers that occurred throughout the region during that time frame. This beetle infestation likely resulted in the removal of substantial quantities of mature conifers within Warner Valley from 2011 to 2016 (Figure 10).

2.3. Index of Historic Late Season Plant Health

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) serves as a standardized remote sensing indicator that can be employed to assess vegetation health and density. NDVI values range between 0 and 1, and Lower values typically signify stress resulting from water scarcity or the onset of drought. The RAP tool provides bi-monthly NDVI estimates derived from Landsat data spanning from 1986. The evaluation of NDVI values for Warner Valley was conducted for September values, as the condition of plants during late summer can serve as an indicator of their response and resilience to hot summer temperatures and water scarcity.

Figure 10. The long-term trend in meadow plant health is depicted by the late-season (September) mean of NDVI values for the Warner Valley meadow. Each point represents this data. Note potential for pattern to be consistent with tree cover.

2.3.1. Long-Term Plant Health Trend and Interpretation

RELATIVELY HIGH NDVI VALUES – Even during the late season of September, NDVI values remain relatively high for the meadow and consistently exceed 0.5.

TEMPORAL TREND MAY BE CONFOUNDED BY CONIFER ENCROACHMENT, CLIMATE, AND MANAGEMENT – The overall trend of increasing plant health (NDVI) values from 1986 to 2021 can be attributed to several factors that are difficult to separate. The consistent increase is in alignment with the

removal of grazing in approximately 1990 (Figure 10) that likely improved vegetation condition. High NDVI values also indicate an increase in conifer and riparian hardwood coverage, which are also increasing within meadow areas during this time-period and subsequently decreased in 2021 due to fire. Additionally, the 2021 period was also characterized by a drought, which is reflected by the NDVI values.

2.4. Historic Aerial Imagery Evaluation

The availability of historic aerial imagery provides a direct visual record that can enable researchers to infer and quantify large-scale, long-term shifts in land cover, vegetation composition, and land use practices by comparing photographs taken decades apart. Approximately 70 years of historic aerial imagery was also evaluated as part of this assessment to directly evaluate any evident long-term trends in meadow or riverscape conditions. Imagery from 1953 and 1975 obtained as single-image files from the [USGS's Earth Explorer](#). More recent 2005 imagery was obtained as part of the NAIP (National Agricultural Imagery Program) program and had a resolution of 1 m per pixel (Figure 11). Historic imagery from 1953 and 1975 were spatially referenced to NAIP imagery and had final resolutions of between 1.5 and 1.9 m per pixel.

Figure 11. Historic aerial imagery sources incorporated into the assessment process. Historic single-frame imagery from 1953 and 1975 were spatially referenced to allow quantitative measurement and mapping of historic riverscape and wet-meadow features.

2.4.1. Historic Aerial Imagery Observations and Interpretation

Given the relatively low resolution of historic imagery it was challenging to directly derive quantitative measurements of feature area and distributions from the time-series of aerial imagery, some general patterns could be observed for both the meadow and the primary channel and floodplain of Warner Valley. General observations include:

SPRING CHANNELIZATION - A reduction in the abundance of established spring flow channels within meadow areas is likely attributed to the increased herbaceous and woody vegetation cover, which is also evident (Figure 12).

BARE GROUND - Bare ground is discernible in the 1953 imagery, particularly in the upstream section of Warner Meadow extending towards the upstream boundary of the CDFG wildlife area. This observation also implies that land ownership and management initiated in the late 1980s has enhanced the condition of the meadow vegetation (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Visual comparison of historic (left) and corresponding contemporary aerial imagery (right panels) used in the assessment of observable changes in meadow composition and condition.

Visual interpretation of historical and contemporary data reveals modifications to the active channel and floodplain:

CHANNEL DYNAMISM – The channel exhibits a migratory pattern within its floodplain, indicating a lack of confinement for a significant portion of its length.

INCREASED WOODY DEBRIS ABUNDANCES – The frequency of woody debris jams has been observed to have risen over time.

RIPARIAN VEGETATION – There has been a noticeable increase in the density of riparian forest and shrubs over time.

INCREASED CHANNEL COMPLEXITY – The complexity of depositional bars and flowpaths/thalwegs has increased, indicating enhanced hydraulic and instream habitat variety and quality.

INCREASED RIVERSCAPE EXTENT – The active channel and floodplain appear to be occupying a larger portion of the accessible valley bottom.

Figure 13 Comparison of historic and contemporary aerial imagery noting conspicuous changes in riparian and channel condition and composition.

3. Current Composition and Condition

The assessment of current meadow and riverscape conditions employed data obtained from direct field observations, high-resolution imagery, and elevation datasets (5.1.2). This comprehensive approach facilitated the expansion of field observations to encompass the entire

assessment area, which was impractically large to be covered on foot during this assessment. Assessment components include a characterization of meadow hydrogeomorphic types, a complete vegetative cover classification, and a detailed evaluation of plant robustness utilizing NDVI data. The assessment also includes a partial evaluation of spring channel conditions and beaver activity within meadow areas (3.4 and 3.5), features that are relevant to meadow management planning (see 4). Remote surveys mapping the distribution of channel and floodplain features are also included as an assessment of riverscape condition (see 3.6).

FIELD VISITS - During the summer of 2025, the assessment team conducted two field visits. The first visit, a preliminary scouting trip, took place in June 2025. The single-day visit consisted of walking a portion of the CDFG wildlife area and a brief visit to Warner Creek at the junction of Kings and Hot Springs Creek. The second field visit was conducted on August 21st and 22nd by two aquatic ecologists from Trout Unlimited, Nick Weber and Jessica Strickland, and aquatic restoration specialist, Sabra Purdy. The visit focused on mapping significant meadow, vegetation, and riverscape features. It also aimed to validate the GIS interpretation of vegetation and fluvial feature distributions and characteristics that have been observed during the desktop portions of this assessment.

HIGH-RESOLUTION IMAGERY - High-resolution imagery representative of current conditions was procured from the SkyFi imagery and analytics service. The 4-band (RGB + NIR) imagery was acquired during September 2024, with a resolution of 12 cm per pixel (Figure 11). This imagery was used in subsequent assessments of meadow and riverscape features.

Figure 14. A gravel bar on Warner Creek shown to compare commercial high-resolution imagery (right panel) to readily available basemap imagery services (e.g., ESRI's imagery basemap).

3.1. Hydrogeomorphic Meadow Typing

The hydrogeomorphic meadow (HGM) classification can be utilized to elucidate the primary processes involved in the formation and long-term sustainability of meadow habitats (Weixelman et al. 2011). The classification within Warner Valley meadow contributes to an understanding of meadow habitats that are present and can be employed to infer how changing environmental conditions or alterations in processes due to disturbance or management might transform a meadow type or jeopardize the loss of meadow function.

Meadow types were delineated according to the USDA Forest Service key for Meadow Hydrogeomorphic Types for the Sierra Nevada and Southern Cascades Ranges in California (Weixelman et al. 2011). This classification splits meadows into 14 distinct types that reflect their unique hydrological and geomorphological origins. Meadows are defined in this classification as being dominated by herbaceous (non-woody) plant communities (typically sedges, grasses, and forbs), supported by either surface water (riparian types) or groundwater (or a mixture of the 2) that in functioning meadows is generally at a depth of less than 1 meter below the ground surface, and that woody vegetation may occur but is not the dominant cover type. Soil type is also a primary classifier for meadow hydrogeomorphic type. Meadows with at least 20-40 cm of organic matter in the top 80 cm of the soil are classified as Peatland type meadows (Fens are included in

this designation). These meadows are very special and have a very shallow water table, are completely saturated for most of the growing season, and can sometimes have unique water chemistry that drives a specific plant community. These are some of the rarest and most important meadows for conservation because peat soils take an extraordinarily long time to develop and can be badly damaged by activities such as livestock grazing or other anthropogenic activities. The distribution of HGM types depends on water source (either surface flow or groundwater) in addition to slope, saturation, subsurface processes, and floodplain processes. The results of these mapping efforts help understand the condition, drivers, and management opportunities for different areas based on HGM types.

Figure 15. Hydrogeomorphic (HGM) meadow types observed and mapped within the Warner Valley wildlife area during August 2025. Descriptions of HGM type expressions within Warner Valley, including associated plant species, are presented in Table 2.

Meadow types were mapped in the field during August 2025 visits to the project area (Figure 16). The mapping effort concentrated on the central portion of the project area and encompassed a significant portion of the CDFW wildlife area. Although spatially incomplete, the assorted meadow types present within Warner Valley are likely all represented by the mapping effort. Table 2 provides a list of those meadow types, a description of their characteristics within Warner Valley, and briefly touches on their potential risks for loss or conversion.

Figure 16. Hydrogeomorphic meadow type extents mapped during an assessment visit in August 2025. Descriptions of HGM type expressions within Warner Valley, including associated plant species, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. HGM meadow types present within the Warner Valley assessment area including their general description, indicator plant species, and a brief assessment of their condition or risk for loss of meadow habitat or conversion to another meadow type.

Meadow Type & Indicator Species	Description and Setting	Condition and Risks
<p>Depressional: Perennial and Seasonal</p> <p><i>Typha spp.</i> <i>Erythranthe spp.</i> <i>Carex spp.</i></p>	<p>Depressions where runoff or groundwater accumulate. Precipitation, overland runoff, or groundwater supplies water inputs. Seasonal Depressional Meadows are saturated for part of the growing season; Perennial Depressional Meadows are saturated for most of the growing season. They differ from Basin Peatlands in having less than 20 cm of peat in the upper 40 cm of the soil. Specific plant community and species present often influenced by water depth.</p>	<p>Depressional wetlands in Warner Valley are found along the transition from higher to lower gradient valley slopes, in small depressions. They are vulnerable to desiccation in drought and declining precipitation, but some areas burned in the Dixie fire, with high moisture levels reducing intensity and creating biochar. Early successional species like <i>Erythranthe guttata</i> are recovering. Management should protect from conifer encroachment and maintain the highest water tables possible, considering adjacent riparian channel conditions.</p>
<p>Riparian: Low, Medium, and High Gradient</p> <p><i>Carex spp.</i> Various forbs <i>Salix and Alnus spp.</i></p>	<p>Herbaceous meadow vegetation near defined stream channels with distinct bed and bank processes, surface water inundation, and hyporheic processes on floodplains. Groundwater and surface water processes support them, with water table depth driven by channel geomorphology. Incised channels (eroded) reduce water table elevation and dry surface soils, shaping plant communities. Water source affects flow variability, sediment transport, and vegetation, with spring-fed channels showing less variability than those from runoff or precipitation. Locally dense willow and alder (riparian hardwood forest) may occur along channels, preferring larger substrate size and well-oxygenated, well-drained soil.</p>	<p>Stream channel structure, gradient, and confinement (incision or entrenchment) significantly influence floodplain connectivity, the primary driver of riparian meadow vegetation community structure. Instream structure, such as wood and beaver dams, also contributes to habitat complexity and function. Riparian meadows are typically the most responsive to structural treatments aimed at altering channel geomorphology. A mismatch in channel size vs. average flows reduces floodplain connectivity, leading to decreased water table elevation, reduced groundwater storage, decreased late-season baseflow, and vegetation community shifts towards drier plant communities, resulting in conifer encroachment and loss of herbaceous meadow habitat. Numerous channels in Warner Valley exhibit slight to moderate channel incision, driving shifts in adjacent vegetation communities away from desired wet meadow conditions. These meadow areas are the most responsive to restoration treatments.</p>

**Subsurface:
Low and Middle Gradient**

Carex spp.
Hydric and mesic forbs

Subsurface meadows are characterized by the absence of a distinct channel with discernible bed and bank morphology. Surface water may be present only seasonally. Ditch, swale, and rill formations may be present, providing seasonal flowpaths for runoff. Shallow groundwater and subsurface flows serve as the primary water sources that support a vegetation community predominantly composed of hydric meadow graminoid species, including sedges, rushes, and wetland grasses.

Subsurface meadows in Warner Valley occur where groundwater and subsurface flows dominate over stream channels. They often border riparian meadows where flooding influence diminishes. These meadows respond to changes in stream channel geomorphology and bed depth due to the close relationship between water table elevation and adjacent channel features. Restoration treatments in adjacent riparian channels benefit subsurface meadows directly and indirectly. However, they are vulnerable to drying, vegetation shifts, conifer encroachment, and soil carbon loss if water table levels drop.

**Peatland: Discharge
Slope and Basin types**

Drosera rotundifolia
Sphagnum spp.
Micranthes californica
Vaccinium uliginosum
Pedicularis groenlandica
Platanthera dilatate

Basins, seeps, discharge slopes, and springs, fens with at least 20 cm of organic soil in the top 40 cm composed of decomposing plant material that breaks down very slowly due to anaerobic conditions, are generally very wet meadows with saturated, broadly inundated surfaces. They are dominated by obligate and facultative wetland graminoid and moss species. These meadows are the rarest and highest conservation value meadows in the Sierra Nevada due to the unique plant communities they support and the very specific water and soil chemistry requirements for their formation.

Although this meadow type is relatively uncommon in Warner Valley, it does occur in isolated locations characterized by fen vegetation indicator species. The most extensive peatland area identified during this assessment was situated within the CDFW property and faces the risk of conversion due to drying conditions. The area exhibits significant dense lodgepole encroachment, often accompanied by high mortality rates, and a decline in late-season soil saturation. Drying, conifer encroachment, and potential conversion influenced by channel incision, loss of water table elevation, and reduced flood frequency in adjacent riparian channels could be mitigated through restoration treatments in the channels. These treatments would enhance water surface elevation, improve floodplain connectivity, and augment groundwater storage.

3.1.1. HGM Type Mapping Interpretation

The HGM assessment encompassed the mapping of approximately 192 acres of the project area, which was centered around the CDFW wildlife area. Most of the mapped coverage fell under riparian meadow types, specifically low gradient (122 acres), middle gradient (29.5 acres), and high gradient (6.9 acres). Riparian meadows are functionally a part of the floodplain area along the mainstem of Warner Creek, as well as the numerous spring channels that originate on the eastern side of the valley. Other meadow types identified included depressional meadows, both perennial and seasonal, covering 6 acres and 0.8 acres, respectively. Subsurface areas were also mapped, encompassing low gradient (4.8 acres) and middle gradient (6 acres), as well as basin peatland covering 15.1 acres.

Figure 17. Distribution of meadow types by area for the incomplete mapping of Warner Valley meadow during the August 2025 field visit.

The most extensive riparian meadow habitat was situated along the mainstem of Warner Creek floodplain, where floodplain processes and groundwater exchange are primarily influenced by the streamflow itself, with groundwater originating from adjacent hillslopes playing a subordinate role. Elevations of the streambed and hydrogeomorphic indicators such as channels, saturated soils, and flood wrack indicate that the floodplain remains active throughout most of the valley bottom. We observed a few areas with channel incision that restricted the stream’s flow. However, the substantial quantity of standing dead trees resulting from beetle kill and the Dixie fire, which will

eventually accumulate in the channel and form substantial woody debris jams in the coming years, may contribute to sediment aggradation within the incised sections of the channel and enhance floodplain connectivity where it is deficient. As significant woody inputs to the main channel of Warner Creek are likely in the coming decade and initiating of major wood restoration treatments in the mainstem will not need to be considered until these developments become apparent. The necessary components are already present to facilitate an upward trajectory in habitat complexity, floodplain activation, and groundwater exchange.

Riparian meadow areas adjacent to spring tributary channels descending the east slope of the valley exhibit varying gradient, entrenchment, and lateral connectivity to their adjacent floodplains. These areas possess the highest potential for restoration treatments that elevate water table levels, enhance lateral connectivity, and increase the frequency of overland flow. Additionally, these channels impact adjacent meadow types, as excessive channel depth functions as a drainage system for surrounding soils, potentially exacerbating the drying of subsurface and peatland regions. This phenomenon is evident on the CDFW parcel, where slight stream channel incision leads to drier soil conditions, evidenced by shifts from hydric (facultative wet and obligate wetland vegetation species) to mesic (facultative and upland species) vegetation, and pervasive conifer encroachment in areas where they can tolerate the soil moisture levels. In this region, the encroaching conifers are predominantly Lodgepole (*Pinus contorta*), which are unable to withstand fully saturated, anaerobic soil conditions but can tolerate high levels of soil moisture, making them pernicious encroachers on drying meadows. This observation is frequently noted in areas where channel incision in streams is detected, accompanied by overly dry conditions for hydric plant communities, particularly in peatland and fen areas, during the late August field visit. High densities of conifer encroachment can exacerbate meadow drying, as lodgepoles can evapotranspire substantial amounts of water (up to 2.5-3.5 liters per hour per tree for trees approximately 100 years old). This creates a positive feedback loop, wherein increased conifer encroachment leads to drier soil, which subsequently facilitates further conifer encroachment. The overcapacity riparian channels are likely remnants of livestock grazing, particularly during the late 19th and early 20th centuries when much of the grazing was unregulated. Aerial imagery from the 1950s clearly demonstrates that channels were widened and likely incised. While significant recovery has occurred since that time, evidence of channel geomorphological impacts persist.

3.2. Landcover Composition Mapping

A combination of desktop mapping and field validation was to develop a spatially continuous representation of vegetative and landcover types throughout the entire project area. Mapping was done on the high-resolution imagery, and validated in the field during the August 2025 field visit (Figure 20). This mapping provides a continuous account of vegetation and landcover types that

can be used to track future changes to composition of Warner Valley in response to restoration, management, or natural disturbance and climate impacts. Descriptions for each of the landcover types are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Description of dominant vegetative cover types found within Warner Valley project area.

PEATLAND – FEN: Groundwater-fed wetlands, characterized by accumulated organic matter (peat), exhibit vegetation patterns significantly influenced by the underlying geology and water chemistry. These wetlands are predominantly dominated by sedges, grasses, and rushes, shrubs almost entirely absent.

RIPARIAN FLOODPLAIN GALLERY FOREST: Riparian floodplain adjacent to the mainstem of Warner Creek; characterized by the presence of black cottonwood, aspen, willow, and red alder. Coniferous trees are also found in this area. The herbaceous understory featuring ferns, sedges, and grasses.

HERBACEOUS MEADOW: Meadow environments characterized by herbaceous forbs, grasses, sedges, and rushes. Small conifers or riparian shrubs (alder and willow) are absent or sparse.

RIPARIAN MEADOW MIXED SHRUB AND CONIFER: Functional riparian wet meadow areas characterized by moderate to dense stands of riparian shrub species predominantly comprising alder and willow. Coniferous overstory also common, occurring in densities ranging from sparse to dense.

CONIFER FOREST: Closed canopy stands of coniferous trees generally outside of riparian or meadow areas.

BARE GROUND OR BURNT: Primarily areas subject to intense burning during the 2021 fire, now exhibit dead conifer snags and proliferation of Whitethorn (Figure 19, *Ceanothus cordulata*).

3.2.1. Landcover Composition Interpretation

HERBACEOUS MEADOW ONE QUARTER OF PROJECT AREA – Despite the decline in herbaceous meadow areas within the Waren Valley project area, these areas still cover 224 acres, which is approximately one-quarter of the project area (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Percent and acres for landcover types mapped throughout the project area.

FEN AREAS ARE A CONSERVATIVE ESTIMATE – The ocular classification of fen areas may be conservative or even an underestimate of the actual abundance of these fragile areas. In reality, some herbaceous meadow areas or even riparian shrub and conifer meadow cover types may contain fen areas that require further field validation.

Figure 19. Mountain Whitethorn (Ceanothus cordulatus) is an eager post-fire colonizer and has become dominant in burnt areas on many of the areas around meadow and riparian areas. While difficult to walk through, it is a nitrogen fixer and helps rebuild soils after a burn and eventually retreats as conifers and other shrubs shade it out.

Figure 20. Map of dominant landcover types throughout Warner Valley meadow. Mapping was conducted using high resolution imagery as verified by field visits.

3.3. Current Plant Health Distribution

High-resolution NIR imagery (Figure 11) was also used to establish a contemporary assessment of riparian vegetation health throughout the project area. This assessment relied on the calculation of the NDVI index (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index).

Figure 21. Visualization and classification of landcover types and vegetation 'vigor' using the NDVI index. NDVI calculation is taken from near-infrared imagery captured Sept. 2024.

NDVI calculations can serve as a rapid and precise method for automating the classification of existing land-cover types within the entire project area. NDVI values can be categorized into classes that correspond to vegetation vigor or moisture content. Additionally, NDVI values can be utilized to quantify the area of bare ground or deceased vegetation and provide a reasonable estimation of surface water area. (see Figure 21 and Figure 22).

Figure 22. Cumulative distribution of 2024 landcover for riverine and meadow zones as classified using NDVI calculated from high-resolution multispectral imagery.

3.3.1. Plant Health Distribution Interpretation

MONITORING INDICATOR – Although the current NDVI plant health/wetness index may not be particularly noteworthy on its own, the accuracy of this assessment offers a means for evaluating future changes in plant health because of any management, restoration, or in response to future climate trends. Responses to any of these stimuli would be based on their distribution in a manner similar to Figure 22 but rearranged to compare the distribution of NDVI values over time or before and after restoration treatment implementation.

SURFACE WATER LOW IN MEADOW ZONE – The distribution of NDVI shows that surface water area is very low in the meadow zone of the project area. With restoration actions intended to create ponding and increase floodplain connectivity the use of NDVI values to quantify surface water increases may serve as an appropriate effectiveness monitoring indicator.

BARE GROUND SURFACE WATER – Slightly more bare ground and surface water is observable in the riparian distribution of NDVI values. These values represent the unvegetated bars within the floodplain and active channel as well as surface flows within the main and non-primary channels of Warner Creek.

3.4. Spring Channel Distribution and Condition

Spring channels throughout the meadow portions of the valley bottom have played a crucial role in preserving riparian, wet-meadow, and fen habitats within the project area. The small spring-channels, which have a channel width of anywhere from 0.2 – 2 m, are currently well-vegetated and stable. However, in many instances, they are slightly incised and vertically disconnected from adjacent valley bottom surfaces from between 0.3 – 1 m. This disconnection could be attributed to historical land-use practices that promoted channelization, such as the removal of structural elements like wood or beaver dams, and a beaver population that may be currently suppressed or entirely absent (see 3.5).

Figure 23. One of many small (~2 feet wide) well-vegetated channels that are relatively narrow, of moderate depth, and vertically disconnected from adjacent riparian surfaces.

As previously mentioned in section 1.1, a significant portion of the spring-channel network exhibits moderate entrenchment and structural simplification. This reduction in connectivity to adjacent meadow surfaces poses a potential threat to the continued preservation of herbaceous meadow and peatland habitats. Furthermore, this characteristic of spring-channels provides continued opportunity for the ongoing encroachment of lodgepole pine throughout the valley's floor.

Figure 24. Location of perennial spring channels mapped throughout the project area. Mapping was done as a combination of field observations and desktop assessment using LiDAR elevation data and imagery. The incomplete maps depicts approximately 4 miles of known spring channel locations.

During this assessment, efforts were made to map the locations of spring channels throughout Warner Valley meadow areas. This was achieved through a combination of field observations and the evaluation of aerial imagery and LiDAR topographic data (see Figure 26 for REM example). A comprehensive map of the spring-channel network will be a valuable resource for guiding structural treatment restoration throughout the meadow system (see section 4 below for restoration treatment approaches). However, considering the vast spatial extent of the meadow, the dense vegetation within it, and the intricate nature of the channel network, a complete census of spring channels was beyond the scope of the current assessment. Nevertheless, the

incomplete inventory of channels provides a useful starting point for planning low-impact restoration treatments (Figure 30).

3.5. Observations of Beaver Activity

No active beaver activity was observed during either of the field visits to the project area in June or August. Residents of Warner Valley also report that no active beaver activity, including cuttings or dam construction, has been observed during the summer of 2025.

RECENT BEAVER ACTIVITY OBSERVATIONS - During the August field visit, several relatively recent observations of beaver activity were recorded. Notably, the remnants of a beaver dam were discovered on one of the spring-fed channels (Figure 24). The dam's extensive presence was evident from the substantial sediment accumulation within the pond. However, it was also discernible that the dam was not undergoing active maintenance by beavers for at least a year, potentially extending beyond that timeframe.

Figure 25. Old beaver chews that include riparian shrubs and conifers can be seen throughout the meadow system along spring-channels.

Historic Beaver Activity Observations – The meadow currently lacks a beaver presence, yet the landscape bears the unmistakable marks of their historical activity in the form of old stumps from riparian trees and conifers. This physical evidence is a testament to the beavers' critical past role in maintaining the meadow's health by enhancing hydrology to sustain riparian vegetation and

form fragile wetland and fen habitats. The enhancement of wetlands would have served as a control measure against the encroachment of conifers, as would the direct felling of conifers.

3.6. Riverscape Condition Assessment

The condition of the riverscape was evaluated through a manual delineation of riverscape features' abundance and distributions within Warner Creek and its floodplain (Figure 22). The data can be utilized to derive simple indices that serve as indicators of 'riverscape health'. The assessment methodologies have been comprehensively described in Weber et al. 2024 and are grounded in the riverscape health principles elucidated in Glassic et al. 2025.

The assessment was conducted utilizing Geographic Information System (GIS) software, employing the high-resolution imagery acquired in September 2024 (see section 5.1.1) as the basis for capturing riverscape observations. The assessment encompassed the quantification of the following riverscape features and associated metrics:

PROPORTION VALLEY BOTTOM ACTIVE PROCESSES – The proportion of the accessible valley bottom exhibiting active fluvial processes (i.e., the extent of the existing floodplain) serves as an indicator of the quantity of aquatic habitat and provides a comprehensive assessment of the condition of the riverscape.

MEANDER LENGTH RATIO – The ratio of the primary channel's length to the valley's length serves as an indicator of geomorphic complexity, dynamism, and the abundance of aquatic habitats.

PRIMARY – NON-PRIMARY CHANNEL RATIO – The ratio of primary to non-primary channels is a measure of channel complexity and floodplain accessibility. Higher values indicate a greater degree of channel complexity and increased anabranch channel formation.

FLOW PATH CONFLUENCE AND DIFLUENCE DENSITY – The density of wetted channel thalweg confluences and difluences suggests a high degree of geomorphic and hydraulic channel complexity.

WOOD AGGREGATE ABUNDANCE – The density and volume of woody debris within the active channel serve as indicators of structural complexity, hydraulic complexity, and the quantity and quality of habitat.

Figure 26. Example of GIS-based riverscape feature mapping using high-resolution imagery and the LiDAR REM as context for mapping active channels, woody debris, and floodplain connectivity.

3.6.1. Riverscape Condition Assessment Interpretation

The assessment of Warner Creek indicates a highly functional riverscape characterized by dynamic river processes, diverse riparian vegetation, and floodplain habitat. The channel exhibits a high degree of geomorphic and hydraulic complexity. However, the assessment also identifies areas where the riverscape could enhance both the quantity and quality of aquatic habitat (Table 4, Figure 26).

LOW WOODY DEBRIS DENSITY - The most compelling indicator of the potential for enhancing geomorphic and channel complexity lies in the woody debris loading metric and its correlation with reference riverscapes or those with minimal management. Notably, wood abundances within

the Warner Creek riverscape are relatively low. As previously mentioned in other sections of this report (see section 2.2.1), the Dixie fire of 2021, along with beetle kills of conifers, is likely to result in substantial increases in woody debris abundances within Warner Creek in the foreseeable future. This increase in wood will likely contribute to the elevation of certain riverscape metrics evaluated in this assessment, specifically hydraulic complexity in the form of channel functions and the formation of additional anabranch channels.

Moderate Channel Geomorphic and Hydraulic Complexity is Likely to Increase– The presence of anabranch channels and the moderate abundance of flow path confluences and diffluences suggest a moderate level of geomorphic and hydraulic complexity within Warner Creek. However, these indices and their associated channel features are likely to increase significantly as more wood enters the channel. By combining the wood with the abundant valley bottom space for the channel to adjust and the stream power (Figure 28) and sediment, Warner Creek has the potential to continue developing a dynamic riverscape that provides abundant and high-quality aquatic habitat.

Table 4. Metrics of 'riverscape health' derived by mapping the distribution and abundance of channel features using historic and contemporary aerial imagery.

Riverscape Metric	Indicator Value for Warner Creek	Status and interpretation
Proportion Valley Bottom Active (%)	70% - 100% of available space active	Excellent - Most of the accessible valley bottom floor exhibits active hydrologic, geomorphic, and riparian fluvial processes. There are basically no confining features or channel incision present limiting the active floodplain extent.
Meander length ratio	Valley Len: 6998 m Channel Len: 12044 m Ratio: ~ 2	Moderate – Twice as much channel length as valley length indicates moderate complexity and habitat quantity.
Primary – non-primary channel ratio	Primary: 8384 m Non-Primary: 3660 m Ratio: ~ 0.40	Moderate – Non-primary anabranch channels are present throughout the system, however channel is still predominately single thread.
Wood aggregate density (m ³ / ha.)	2 – 10 (m ³ / ha.)	Low - Moderate – Currently low to moderate throughout much of the project area. Likely to increase as burn wood is recruited.
Flow Path Complexity (confluence / diffluence / km)	149 Junctions 21 Junctions / km	Low - Moderate – Suggests a moderate amount of hydraulic complexity. This metric is expected to increase substantially with increased woody debris abundances.

Figure 27. In contrast, when comparing Warner Creek’s wood loading (m³/ha.) to wood loading values for unmanaged (reference) and lightly managed riverscapes from Wohl et al. (2017) dry conifer forests in the Pacific Northwest, it is evident that Warner Creek’s wood loading remains relatively low in comparison to the reference watersheds. Despite the presence of a significant amount of woody debris pieces and jams, Warner Creek’s wood loading is still likely to be lower than that of unmanaged watersheds.

4. Restoration and Management

This assessment demonstrated that the riverscape and meadow systems within Warner Valley are in a favorable ecological state, providing an abundance of positive ecosystem services and offering high-quality aquatic and terrestrial habitats. Consequently, restoration recommendations should be limited to low-impact process-based solutions that pose no risk of damaging existing sensitive habitats. The restoration recommendations presented below for the Warner Valley riverscape, and meadow systems adhere to principles of low-tech process-based practices (Wheaton et al. 2019), which are simple, cost-effective, and utilize natural materials. These recommendations would be implemented without the use of machinery that could potentially damage fragile aquatic resources. In addition to restoration and management, this section also includes an inventory of culverts and associated spring channels, detailing their interaction with the Warner Valley Road on the eastern side of the valley (see section 4.3).

Figure 28. Estimated flood recurrence interval from StreamStats model estimates for Warner Creek within the CDFW wildlife management area. The large floods that are relatively common within Warner Creek could make any restoration treatments in the active channel difficult, especially for LTPBRT treatments that would be implemented without the use of heavy equipment.

4.1. Restoration Planning within the Warner Creek Riverscape

As previously mentioned in the Riverscape Assessment section (see section 3.6.1), Warner Creek and its associated floodplain currently exhibit a relatively high degree of fluvial function and provide quality habitat for aquatic and terrestrial species within Warner Valley. The riverscape is free of confining features, exhibits little to no channel incision, and is also free of any extractive water use or modifications of its natural flow regime. With Warner Creek potentially being slightly low in terms of its abundance of woody debris, only treatments that would expedite the processes of wood accumulation are considered. Several low-tech process-based wood treatment scenarios, their associated risks and opportunities are listed in Table 5. The treatment types include doing nothing, and allowing processes of wood accumulation to commence naturally, to more intensive wood treatment approaches that might include securing woody debris in the channel to further enhance processes of woody debris accumulation.

Table 5. Candidate low-tech process-based restoration practices that might be considered for the Warner Creek riverscape active channel and its floodplain.

<i>Restoration Alternative</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Risks</i>
<i>Preserve Natural Processes Do Nothing</i>	Allow natural processes to continue the positive trajectory of the Warner Creek riverscape. Do nothing.	Low-cost and low-risk, positive processes of wood accumulation are already occurring.	Enhancement of riverscape habitat quality may take time, but it is already quite good, so that is acceptable.
<i>Woody Debris Seeding</i>	Enhance rates of woody debris recruit by direct felling standing dead trees within the active channel and floodplain.	Expedites process of wood accumulation, low-cost, and low-risk ecologically and financially.	Very little risk, treatment is low cost and simply expediting natural processes. Some risk to downstream infrastructure like bridges should be considered.
<i>Structural Treatment Construction</i>	Direct construction of woody debris jams utilizing local wood. Could be either hand-built (difficult) or engineered and installed with equipment	May expedite processes of wood accumulation. Allow targeted treatment of areas of low-habitat quality. Hand-built would be largely ineffective in such a large system	Engineered approach would require considerable design and implementation expense. Risk of failure with high-flows and high stream power of Warner Creek. Hand-built structures would likely be largely ineffective.

Figure 29. Two examples of beaver dam analogs that mimic beaver activity. Implementation of this low-impact meadow management approach within the spring-channels of Warner Valley meadow would encourage expansion and enhancement of wet-meadow habitat, contribute to reduction of existing and prevent further encroachment of conifers. The examples shown here are built using conifer branches and do not use driven posts making their installation particularly low-impact on surrounding meadow habitat.

4.2. Restoration Planning within Warner Valley Meadow

Restoration recommendations for the Warner Valley meadow should be aimed at enhancing the extent of wet-meadow habitat which would also halt the process of conifer encroachment. These processes could be achieved over time by mimicking and promoting beaver activity. Mimicking beaver activity would be achieved through implementation of beaver dam analog structures within spring channels throughout the meadow. The structures could be built using the limbs of the conifers that are felled during conifer reduction treatments. As trapping restrictions are already in place in Warner Valley, promotion of beaver activity would include reintroduction of problem beavers captured in other areas.

Table 6. Candidate low-tech process-based restoration practices that might be considered for the Warner Valley meadow for mimicking and promoting beaver activity.

<i>Restoration Alternative</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Risks</i>
<i>Preserve Natural Processes Do Nothing</i>	No additional treatments are required. Continue management of Warner Valley.	Riverscapes and meadows are already in favorable ecological conditions.	The trajectory of diminishing wet-meadow habitat and conifer encroachment is likely to persist. Considering the potential climate impacts, the rate of change may also accelerate.
<i>BDA Treatments in Spring Channels</i>	Initiate the treatment of hand-built BDA structures, specifically targeting the entrenched spring channels.	A cost-effective and minimally disruptive approach is proposed to enhance positive hydrologic and geomorphic processes. This approach aims to increase the functionality and extent of wet meadows while simultaneously reducing the rate of conifer encroachment.	Structural treatments would be cost-effective and pose minimal ecological risk, if any.
<i>Conifer Thinning</i>	The direct thinning and felling of conifers employing hand tools.	Thinning activities, when conducted manually, pose minimal economic or ecological risks. Additionally, provide a source of BDA building materials.	The substantial expanse of coniferous forests will pose significant challenges to impact without substantial resource allocation.
<i>Beaver Reintroduction</i>	Reintroduce or subsidize beaver populations originating from regions where their presence is undesirable or problematic.	The establishment of beaver colonies within the meadow presents the most optimal solution for long-term self-sustaining processes that would enhance and preserve the diverse meadow habitat in Warner Valley.	The establishment of beavers poses a risk to infrastructure such as culverts. Trapping and relocating beavers necessitate substantial resource investment for planning and execution.

4.3. Hill Slope Instability and Culvert Condition

An inventory of all culverts and their associated drainage channels was conducted across the east side of the valley to document current conditions and provide a critical baseline for future engineering work. The primary goal of this initial assessment was to identify and catalog all existing road-stream crossings, which will serve as the starting point for a professional engineer evaluation. Consideration should also be given to invoking the county or other governmental entities that might have capacity to support road and culvert repairs and mitigation.

This evaluation is a first step toward proper design, repair or replacement of failing culverts that would mitigate ongoing damage to the valley's road infrastructure and minimize negative impacts on stream and meadow hydrology. During the assessment, twelve culverts and channels were evaluated. Four culverts, primarily associated with perennial channels, were found to be in critical condition and required immediate attention (Table 7).

Figure 30. A perennial spring channel and its associated culvert has been affected by the loss of vegetation after the fire in 2021. As a result, increased channelization and sediment transport have led to several culverts becoming clogged, unstable, and ineffective.

Figure 31. Culvert location, condition, and status for those evaluated within upstream reaches of Warner Valley.

Table 7. Culvert evaluations for slope instability, culvert clogging, and general condition. Culvert locations can be found in Figure 31.

Name	Description
<p data-bbox="518 1457 732 1524">Culvert-01 <i>Needs Attention</i></p>	Large double culvert is functional but at high flows channel will continue to erode unstable berms and banks.
<p data-bbox="518 1726 732 1793">Culvert-02 <i>Needs Attention</i></p>	Small culvert, evidence of increased sedimentation due to fire and vegetation loss. Culvert probably %30 filled but remains functional.

Culvert-03
Needs Attention

Some evidence of increased down cutting erosion and channelization from vegetation loss, however culvert remains functional.

Culvert-04
Critical

The erosion of the slope trench has resulted in the significant accumulation of material on the road, causing a fan-like obstruction. The exposed slope has led to an increase in sediment clogging the culvert and sediment deposition over the road. The imminent failure of the culvert and damage to the road are a serious concern.

Culvert-05
Critical

Vegetation loss and instability have led to erosion and head cutting at the culvert. The culvert hanging has resulted in downcutting. The hillslope exhibits extensive erosion due to the loss of vegetation.

Culvert-06
Critical

A substantial erosive steep draw with minimal vegetation is present. Currently, the draw is actively downcutting and depositing material, which is subsequently moving over the road. The culvert is largely obstructed, and the head cutting downstream of the road crossing is also causing erosion of the road.

Culvert-07
Critical

The culvert is currently obstructed by sediment, and the spring-fed flow is overflowing the existing road. While the perennial flow contributes to revegetation and soil stability, the culvert and road require repair.

Culvert-08
Functional

Small culvert is situated in a well-vegetated spring channel.

Culvert-09
Functional

Small culvert of spring channel appears functional, stable, and well vegetated.

Culvert-10
Functional

Culvert in good condition and in well vegetated spring channel.

Culvert-11
Needs Attention

Very small culvert at well vegetated spring channel. Culvert appears functional but some clogging with sediment and vegetation is present.

Culvert-12
Functional

Small stable spring channel, culvert appears to be functioning well.

5. Conclusion

Although somewhat technical, this assessment aims to provide a quantitative account of the current ecological condition of Warner Valley’s meadow and riverscape environments, thereby guiding management and tracking future changes. We hope this report serves as a foundation for the development of low-impact, nature-based restoration and management solutions that preserve and enhance the remarkable and diverse natural value and significant wonder of Warner Valley. We believe that by adopting thoughtful, process-based restoration solutions that are guided by the inherent wisdom of the landscape, there exists a tangible opportunity to reverse subtle declines and ensure the vibrant preservation of the Warner Valley fen and wet meadow habitats and other significant ecological resources for future generations of people and wildlife.

Figure 32. This image underscores a significant finding of the assessment: the gradual drying of meadow environments within Warner Valley and the gradual expansion of conifers across the valley floor

Appendix I: Imagery and Digital Datasets

The following is a comprehensive list of imagery, elevation, and other Geographic Information System (GIS) datasets that depict meadow and riverscape features utilized in this assessment. The authors intend for these datasets to serve as a foundation for future analysis of meadow condition and composition, or two assist with restoration and/or management planning.

5.1.1. Aerial Imagery Datasets

Historic aerial imagery was procured using the USGS’s the National Map application. Imagery was spatially referenced to allow evaluation in most GIS software.

<i>Imagery</i>	<i>Acquisition Date</i>	<i>Bands</i>	<i>Resolution</i>
USGS 1953	Oct. 25 th , 1953	Greyscale	1.5 m
USGS 1975	Sept. 20 th , 1975	Greyscale	1.9 m
NAIP 2005	Aug. 8 th , 2005	RGB	1 m
SkyFi 2024	Sept. 2024	RGB + NIR	12 cm

5.1.2. Elevation Datasets

LiDAR data with a resolution of 1 m was also procured using the USGS’s National Map application. [The LiDAR data was acquired in 2022](#). The relative elevation model (REM) was generated using the Geomorphic Gradeline method in ArcGIS Pro (Powers 2013).

5.1.3. Vector Datasets Used in Meadow and Riverscape Assessments

All vector datasets generated during this assessment are accessible in a single geopackage that can be consumed within most GIS software (Table 8).

Table 8. Vector layers generated as part of this assessment including their inclusion in analyses.

<i>Layer</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Assessment Boundary</i>	Boundary serves as the limit of the assessment, approximates the valley bottom.
<i>Process Zones</i>	Extent of riverscape (i.e., Warner Creek floodplain and active channel) or meadow process zones

<i>Centerline</i>	Approximate center of valley bottom, used to measure and scale to project length
<i>HGM Types</i>	Boundaries of hydrogeomorphic meadow types as mapped in the field.
<i>Land Cover Types</i>	Extent of landcover classifications mapped from 2024 imagery
<i>Riverscape Channel Junctions</i>	Flow path (thalweg) confluence and diffluence mapped from 2024 imagery for the riverscape assessment.
<i>Riverscape Channels</i>	Primary and anabranch channel mapping from 2025 imagery
<i>Riverscape Wood Aggregates</i>	Wood aggregates mapped from 2024 imagery with estimated number of pieces and aggregate width.
<i>Warner Culverts</i>	Field mapped culverts along Warner Valley Road.
<i>Warner Spring Channels</i>	Incomplete map of spring channels

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